

Model-based approach for indentation on soft electronic skin[☆]

Chiara Micheli^{a,*}, Giovanni Berselli^b, Lucia Seminara^a

^a Department of Naval, Electric, Electronic and Telecommunication Engineering, University of Genova, Genova, 16145, Italy

^b Department of Mechanical, Energy, Management and Transportation Engineering, University of Genova, Genova, 16145, Italy

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

PVDF tactile sensors
Soft electronic skin
Finite element model analysis
Normal force reconstruction
Indentation experiments

ABSTRACT

The primary objective of this research is to develop a model-based framework for the indentation on the surface of a soft electronic skin. In the current paper, the model has been applied to a soft electronic skin embedding piezoelectric polymer (PVDF, polyvinylidene fluoride) transducers. We revisit in a dimensionless fashion an analytical solution of the problem presented in a previous contribution for a normal force (frictionless case) and extend the analysis to account for a tangential component of the contact force (frictional case). First, the transmission of Hertzian distributed forces through the skin elastomer layer to a PVDF transducer is analyzed, assuming a half-space model for the elastomer. Then, the above mathematical formulation has been employed to perform extensive FEM simulations such to extend the analytical solutions for the half-space case to the real configuration where the elastomer layer has finite thickness and the transducer is not necessarily vertically aligned with the indenter. The model is applied to the case of a dragon skin, a well-known soft alternative to the silicone-based PDMS e-skin discussed in the previous paper. The model can be easily extended to other sensor types, provided the transducer is integrated on a rigid substrate and converts the pressure acting on its upper surface into a proportional electrical signal. The present framework is a first step towards the construction of a general design tool for soft electronic skins based on pressure transducers, regardless of the specific transducer type and material employed for the soft cover.

1. Introduction

The human hand is a highly versatile system that serves as an excellent model for the artificial reconstruction of the sense of touch. The concept of biomimicry needs to be interpreted and a principled simplification in both design and control is possible to reduce the complexity of exactly reproducing the appearance and dexterity of human hands [1]. However, as the hand behaviors such as grasping and manipulation primarily rely on contact, the capabilities of a robotic hand are constrained by the characteristics of the artificial skin [2], especially on its fingers. Such features include the hand being provided with a soft interface embedding mechanoreceptors with different frequency bandwidths, possibly covering the whole human tactile bandwidth ranging from static contacts to time-varying contacts at frequencies of the order of the kilohertz [3,4]. Robotic hands equipped with soft artificial skin enable enhanced and human-like haptic interactions with the surrounding environment. The soft interface mainly provides increased contact surfaces such that the robotic hand conforms to the irregular shape of the object and allows to obtain more stable grips. Tactile sensors collect data as the artificial hand mechanically interacts with objects or surfaces. Note that, below, the word “sensor” has

been employed to describe the aggregate of functional and structural elements that constitute the electronic skin, while “transducer” is used for the functional element itself (eg PVDF).

There has been a longstanding significant interest in developing electronic skin systems that focus on inferring quantities related to the mechanical contact over the skin surface. Indeed, contact forces, induced skin displacements, and spread rate of contact area are particularly interesting tactile cues for haptic perception. Let us mention some of the recent important contributions to the subject. An artificial intelligence based biomimetic soft skin was developed by Oddo's group [5]. Photonic fiber Bragg grating transducers mimicking the functionality of human Ruffini mechanoreceptors are embedded in a curved and soft polymeric matrix. A deep learning algorithm based on convolutional neural networks has been used to interpret sensor outputs. This system enables to estimate both the magnitude and localization of contact forces on the skin surface. Another recent interesting development is a bio-inspired electronic skin mimicking the interlocked dermis-epidermis interface in the human skin [6]. Together with providing increased sensitivity and minimizing hysteresis, this 3D and soft sensing structure is capable of measuring and discriminating both normal and

[☆] This paper was recommended for publication by Associate Editor Oliver Sawodny.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: chiara.micheli@edu.unige.it (C. Micheli).

tangential forces in real-time. The same option of estimating normal and shear forces, and thus also determine slip states, is available through the GelSight sensor [7], consisting of a transparent elastomer slab, coated with a reflective material. A camera is used to capture the distortion of the reflective membrane due to the applied mechanical stimulus. A high-resolution image effectively shows the 3D topography of the object surface in contact with the sensor. Moreover, this sensing system allows one to estimate how the contact area changes over time. The contact area spread rate is highly significant for haptic discrimination of softness in humans [8]. The same principle has also been used [9] to provide a model-based approach for compliance discrimination via soft tactile optical sensing (Tactip sensor [10]) and optical flow computation. The most general contact information that can be derived from an artificial skin is a distribution map of the force vector, which has been reconstructed e.g. over the entire conical sensing surface of the Insight sensor by Kuckenbecker's group [11]. Contact force distributions over the surface of an electronic skin can also be reconstructed using model-based approaches as in [12]. The solution of an ill-posed inverse problem was obtained through an optimization procedure accounting for the physical features of the system.

In the present article, we improve on our previous model [13], where an electronic skin was considered consisting of a sensor array based on PVDF (Polyvinylidene fluoride) piezoelectric polymers, coupled to a rigid substrate and covered by an elastic layer. A rigid indenter acted on the upper surface of the elastic layer generating a normal force distribution modeled as Hertzian. The distributed normal force transmitted to the extended PVDF sensor was calculated through an analytical approach based on a Boussinesq half-space assumption for the elastic layer. Preliminary FEM simulations were also provided to extend the analysis to the actual configuration where the elastic layer has finite thickness. **Here, we pursue the ultimate goal of developing a predictive model and a general tool for design, calibration and contact force reconstruction** for artificial skins, where both the normal and tangential tactile stimuli applied on the outer surface of the soft cover layer are received by the transducers as a pressure on their upper side. It is noteworthy that the present model is not restricted by the sensor type, provided that the transducer is integrated on a rigid substrate and converts pressure into a proportional electrical signal. The mathematical problem is reformulated in a novel dimensionless form that shows that the response of the electronic skin can be expressed in terms of a single dynamical dimensionless parameter, for given values of further dimensionless parameters describing the system geometry. The previous analysis for normal forces (frictionless) is extended in two ways. On one hand, it is no longer assumed that the indenter is vertically aligned with the transducer. On the other hand, the presence of both normal and tangential components of the applied force (frictional case) is considered. The newly formulated mathematical problem is then solved by an extensive set of numerical simulations. This also allows us to point out some limitations of the previous approach, due to the lack of a convergence study resulting in choosing a mesh that was not optimized.

The rest of the present paper proceeds as follows. The next Section illustrates the structure of our e-skin. Then, the analytical solution of the problem developed under the half-space assumption in [13] is revisited in a dimensionless fashion. Also, the previous frictionless analysis is extended to the frictional case. The latter formulations are then employed to guide the finite element numerical approach for the finite thickness case, described in Section 2.4. Section 3 is devoted to presenting and discussing our present results along with some comparison with our previous achievements. How these numerical models can be used as basic tools for sensor design, calibration and force reconstruction is treated in Section 4. Some conclusions and indications for further future steps will follow in Section 5.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Electronic skin material and structure

A basic skin architecture is considered, which includes a rigid substrate, an array of pressure transducers and a soft protective layer on top, as shown in Fig. 1.

Below, both analytical and numerical mathematical models are developed to determine how a force F exerted by a rigid spherical indenter on the upper surface of the soft protective layer is transmitted to the array of pressure transducers, located at the bottom of the layer. This allows us to evaluate the average normal stress acting on these transducers. Knowledge of the transducer constitutive relationship then enables to translate the average normal stress into an electrical output. As a result, a correlation is established between the external load and the electrical output. As sketched in Fig. 1, the latter correlation may be used to solve two distinct problems. On one hand, one may use this model as a design tool, notably to optimize the materials and geometry of the sensor array (taxel radius, pitch, spatial arrangement; thickness of the soft layer; ...) for given application requirements. On the other hand, the present model is a prerequisite to tackle the inverse problem, namely reconstructing the magnitude and direction of the contact force from the outputs of an array of transducers.

In the following, the focus is on PVDF (polyvinylidene fluoride) transducers, whose fabrication process has been described in details in [14]. PVDF transducers can detect mechanical changes and convert them into electrical signals due to their piezoelectric properties. They measure dynamic contacts and transient events, covering the whole frequency range of all human mechanoreceptors, except for very low values (say 0.5 Hz–1 kHz) [15]. Due to the orthotropic PVDF symmetry and small typical layer thickness, when integrated on a rigid substrate these transducers work in thickness mode, such that [16]:

$$Q = d_{33} \bar{T}_3 \pi r_t^2 \quad (1)$$

Here, Q is the total charge on the sensor surface orthogonal to the film thickness, \bar{T}_3 is the average normal stress component on the transducer surface (taken as positive if compressive), d_{33} is the piezoelectric coefficient and r_t is the transducer radius. Hence, in thickness-mode, these transducers meet the criterion of directly converting the acting pressure into an electrical signal, specifically a charge. Electronic circuits for data acquisition are then based on charge amplifiers [17]. Note that Eq. (1) concerns only how the PVDF transducer converts the received stress \bar{T}_3 into a charge. It is not subject to any constraint on the position of the applied force with respect to the transducer axis. The latter affects only the way the soft protective layer transmits the load information determining the stress field \bar{T}_3 intercepted by a set of transducers.

The role of the soft protective layer is the mechanical filtering of the tactile stimulus applied on the skin surface. Mimicking the characteristics of the human skin, the soft layer distributes the mechanical stimulus onto the transducer array below, while protecting the transducers themselves, thus making the skin system compliant, robust and able to interact safely with the environment. Below, the behavior of two different silicon-based materials will be compared: (i) a PDMS layer (already considered in [13]) as an elastomer cover for PVDF tactile transducers; (ii) the widely used dragon skin (see eg. [5] for the skin of a robotic forearm), which could be eligible for a novel soft version of our PVDF-based e-skin.

2.2. Analytical model of the indentation process: the case of a purely normal force (frictionless)

Fig. 2 provides a visual representation of the way the indentation process has been analytically modeled in [13]. The soft protective layer of the sensor, rather than being bounded by a substrate, is assumed to consist of a layer of an elastic medium (Young's modulus E) filling the

Fig. 1. Illustrative sketch of the sensing system and the general scopes of this work.

Fig. 2. Modeling the indentation process.

half-space bounded by the free surface on which the load is applied. The transducer depth below the free surface of the layer is denoted by h . The protective layer is assumed to consist of an incompressible elastic medium, i.e. characterized by a Poisson ratio ν sufficiently close to 0.5. The rigid hemispherical indenter of radius R exerts the normal force F_3 on the e-skin surface. Note that the vertical axis in Fig. 2 points downward, hence F_3 is positive if the contact force is compressive (as in all indentation processes). This choice of the reference system corrects an ambiguity that was present in [13] where F_3 was taken as a positive quantity independently of the chosen direction of the vertical axis.

The radius a of the imprint is related to the applied load as follows [18]:

$$a = \sqrt[3]{\frac{3F_3 R(1-\nu)^2}{4E}} \quad (2)$$

Eq. (1) shows that the transducer charge output is proportional to the average normal stress \bar{T}_3 . The model presented in [13] allows one to calculate \bar{T}_3 in terms of the function σ , which is a measure of how the normal distributed force F_3 is transmitted to the transducer through the protective layer:

$$\sigma\left(\frac{a}{h}, \frac{r_t}{h}\right) = \frac{\bar{T}_3 2\pi h^2}{3F_3} \quad (3)$$

Note that σ is a function of the contact radius a and of the transducer radius r_t , both scaled by the transducer depth h . The latter result deserves some comments. Eq. (3) is a dimensionless rather than dimensional relationship. This approach will be employed throughout the whole paper. Indeed, seeking solutions in dimensionless form is an extremely powerful tool when one deals with a phenomenon that depends on several dimensional variables. As a result of non-dimensionalization, the effort required to determine, numerically or experimentally, the dependence of the sought function (σ , in the present case) on the variables of the problem is strongly reduced. This is further discussed below.

In [13] the validity of the assumption that the transducer is immersed within an elastic half-space rather than lying on the interface between a protective layer of finite thickness h and an underlying substrate was briefly analyzed. It is important to note that, in the finite thickness case, the underlying rigid substrate modifies one of the boundary conditions of the problem. For such reason, as discussed in [13] (sect. 2.4) numerical results for the finite thickness case must be interpreted using a more general dimensionless relationship for the function σ :

$$\sigma = \sigma\left(\frac{R}{h}, \frac{r_t}{h}, L\right) \quad (4)$$

This relationship is readily found (see [13]) noting that the stress on a transducer vertically aligned with the contact force must depend on the load F_3 , on the thickness of the protective layer h and its elastic modulus E , as well as on the size of the contact area R and the transducer radius r_t . Simple dimensional arguments (with the help of Buckingham theorem) then lead to Eq. (4). Note that this relationship involves the new dimensionless parameter L , which reads:

$$L = \frac{F_3}{R^2 E} \quad (5)$$

In Fig. 3 σ is plotted as a function of the dimensionless parameter L , for different values of R/h and a given value of r_t/h ($=0.5$), based on the analytical half-space model discussed in [13]. This plot replaces the plots for σ vs. a/h contained in [13]. The reader is explicitly referred

Fig. 3. The function σ is plotted versus L , for different values of R/h and a given value of r_t/h ($=0.5$). The values of σ have been calculated using the half-space model presented in [13].

to Section 3.2, where this plot has been thoroughly commented and interpreted.

Of course, similar plots can be obtained for any value of r_t/h .

In Section 3.1, we will systematically compare the half-space model with the finite thickness model on the basis of numerical simulations.

Once σ is numerically evaluated from the above plot, the average normal stress can be deduced inverting Eq. (3):

$$\bar{T}_3 = \frac{3}{2\pi} \frac{F_3}{h^2} \sigma\left(\frac{R}{h}, \frac{r_t}{h}, L\right) \quad (6)$$

Note that, so far, our analysis applies to any transducer type, as it only describes how the mechanical indentation action on the e-skin surface is transmitted to the transducer through the elastomer layer. Below, the focus is on a specific transducer, namely PVDF piezoelectric polymers, and a dimensionless variable is derived that can be easily expressed as a function of the measured transducer charge.

Substituting from Eqs. (5) and (6) into Eq. (1), one finds:

$$Q = \frac{3}{2} d_{33} ER^2 \left(\frac{r_t}{h}\right)^2 L \sigma \quad (7)$$

It is then natural to make the latter equation dimensionless in the form:

$$\hat{Q} = \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{r_t}{h}\right)^2 L \sigma \quad (8)$$

where \hat{Q} is defined as follows:

$$\hat{Q} = \frac{Q}{d_{33} ER^2} \quad (9)$$

With the help of Fig. 3 (which refers to our half-space analytical model), Fig. 4 allows one to determine the dimensionless charge response as a function of the parameter L for any given values of the parameters r_t/h and R/h .

In Fig. 4 the dimensionless charge response is plotted.

The Figs. 3 and 4 are the major output of the half-space model for purely normal forces revisited in the present contribution in a more general form.

As mentioned above, the half space model is only qualitatively valid when applied to protective layers of e-skins, which are characterized by finite thickness. Moreover, for transducers working in thickness mode, the finite layer is bounded by a rigid substrate which imposes a boundary condition at the bottom interface of the e-skin. In Section 2.4, the limits of the half-space model will be overcome by resorting to the use of a numerical approach.

Fig. 4. The analytical solution for \hat{Q} is plotted as a function of L for different values of R/h and $r_t/h = 0.5$. The half-space model has been employed to evaluate σ .

Fig. 5. Schematic view of the point-like transducer and point force.

2.3. Extension to the frictional case

Thus far, our discussion has been confined to purely normal indenting forces (frictionless case), further assuming that the indenter was aligned with the transducer. Below, numerical simulations will be conducted such to account for both the effects of tangential and off-center indentation relative to the transducer. Before proceeding to that numerical extension, it is instructive to derive the form of the analytical half-space model for forces oriented arbitrarily, thus possessing both tangential and normal components (frictional case). To this aim, let us revisit equations 3, 4 in [13].

2.3.1. The case of point force and point transducer

The Boussinesq solution for the stress field T induced in an elastic half-space by a point force F acting on the upper surface takes the form [19] :

$$\mathbf{T} = \frac{3}{2\pi} \frac{\mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{e}_r}{r^2} \mathbf{e}_r \otimes \mathbf{e}_r \quad (10)$$

where r is the radial distance of the generic point of the medium from the application point of the load F , \mathbf{e}_r is the unit vector in the r -direction and \otimes is the symbol of tensor product.

Below, it will be assumed that Eq. (10) may be applied to our finite thickness protective layer.

Let us then refer to Fig. 5 for notations.

Note that the unit vector in the vertical direction, as well as the radial vector \mathbf{r} connecting the application point of the force to the transducer center and the associated unit vector \mathbf{e}_r , point downward. Since \hat{r} is the projection of \mathbf{r} onto the transducer plane, we have $r^2 = \hat{r}^2 + h^2$.

With the latter notations, the unit vector \mathbf{e}_r reads:

$$\mathbf{e}_r = \sin \alpha (\cos \beta \cdot \mathbf{e}_1 + \sin \beta \cdot \mathbf{e}_2) + \cos \alpha \cdot \mathbf{e}_3 \quad (11)$$

with $\cos \alpha = h/r$ and $\sin \alpha = \hat{r}/r$. Hence, expressing $\mathbf{e}_r \otimes \mathbf{e}_r$ and $\mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{e}_r$, one readily finds:

$$\mathbf{T} = \frac{3}{2\pi} \frac{(F_1 \cos \beta + F_2 \sin \beta) \hat{r} + F_3 h}{r^3} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\hat{r}^2}{r} (\cos \beta)^2 & \frac{\hat{r}^2}{r} \cos \beta \sin \beta & \frac{\hat{r} h}{r} \cos \beta \\ \frac{\hat{r}^2}{r} \cos \beta \sin \beta & \frac{\hat{r}^2}{r} (\sin \beta)^2 & \frac{\hat{r} h}{r} \sin \beta \\ \frac{\hat{r} h}{r} \cos \beta & \frac{\hat{r} h}{r} \sin \beta & \frac{h^2}{r} \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

Finally, the stress acting on a surface normal to \mathbf{e}_3 is found to read:

$$\mathbf{t} = \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{e}_3 = \frac{3}{2\pi} \frac{(F_1 \cos \beta + F_2 \sin \beta) \hat{r} + F_3 h}{r^3} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\hat{r} h}{r} \cos \beta \\ \frac{\hat{r} h}{r} \sin \beta \\ \left(\frac{h}{r}\right)^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

In particular, the normal component t_3 (or T_3) of the stress vector acting on the transducer has the form:

$$t_3 = T_3 = \frac{3}{2\pi h^2} \frac{(F_1 \cos \beta + F_2 \sin \beta) \lambda + F_3}{(\lambda^2 + 1)^{\frac{5}{2}}} \quad (14)$$

having denoted by λ the ratio \hat{r}/h .

Below, for the sake of simplicity, it will be assumed that β is equal to zero and the tangential component is aligned with \mathbf{e}_1 .

Eq. (14) clarifies that the tangential component of the applied force gives rise to an additional contribution to the stress T_3 felt by the transducer. As the effect of the normal force component has been clarified previously, the present section will concentrate only on the contribution of the tangential component. Under this condition, and noting that $F_1 = \mu F_3$ (μ is the friction coefficient for the silicone-based soft cover), Eq. (14) becomes:

$$T_3 = \frac{3}{2\pi h^2} \frac{\lambda}{(\lambda^2 + 1)^{\frac{5}{2}}} \mu F_3 \quad (15)$$

It is worth noting that the contribution of the tangential force to T_3 vanishes as $\hat{r} = 0$, i.e. if the point of application of F_1 and the point-like transducer are vertically aligned. In other words, under these conditions, a concentrated tangential force does not affect the normal stress at the transducer.

2.3.2. Effect of a tangential force distributed over a circular contact area on a point-like transducer

Let us next assume that the tangential force F_1 is distributed on a circular contact area of radius a .

The goal is to calculate the normal stress at a transducer located at a distance r from the contact center. The infinitesimal element of the contact area is: $\tilde{r} d\tilde{r} d\theta$ (Fig. 6(b)).

The normal stress at the single-point transducer can then be calculated by integrating the infinitesimal contributions associated with each element of the contact area.

Assuming a Hertzian distribution for the normal force, the tangential contribution per unit area q_1 reads:

$$q_1(\tilde{r}) = \mu q_n(\tilde{r}) = \mu q_z \left\{ 1 - \frac{\tilde{r}^2}{a^2} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (16)$$

where μ is the friction coefficient and q_n is the Hertzian distribution of the normal force per unit area, with q_z as its maximum value.

As the normal force F_3 reads:

$$F_3 = \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \int_0^a q_n(\tilde{r}) \tilde{r} d\tilde{r} \quad (17)$$

with the help of Eq. (16) one finds:

$$q_z = \frac{3}{2\pi} \frac{F_3}{a^2} \quad (18)$$

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. Schematic view of the case of a distributed tangential force with a single point transducer.

and Eq. (16) can be written as:

$$q_1(\tilde{r}) = \frac{3\mu F_3}{2\pi a^2} \left\{ 1 - \frac{\tilde{r}^2}{a^2} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (19)$$

The radius a of the imprint is related to the applied load F_3 through Eq. (2).

With the notations of Fig. 6 and recalling Eq. (15) one finds:

$$dT_3 = \frac{3}{2\pi h^2} \frac{\tilde{r}'}{h} q_1(\tilde{r}) \tilde{r} d\tilde{r} d\theta \cos \beta' \quad (20)$$

where β' is the angle shown in Fig. 6, which is a function of anomaly θ by the relation:

$$\hat{r} = \tilde{r}' \cos \beta' + \tilde{r} \cos \theta \quad (21)$$

Replacing $\tilde{r}' \cos \beta'$ from (21) into (20) and using Carnot's theorem to express λ'^2 one readily finds:

$$T_3 = \frac{3}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \int_0^{a/h} \frac{q_1(\tilde{\lambda}) (\lambda - \tilde{\lambda} \cos \theta) \tilde{\lambda} d\tilde{\lambda}}{[\lambda^2 + \tilde{\lambda}^2 - 2\lambda\tilde{\lambda} \cos \theta + 1]^{\frac{5}{2}}} = \delta(\lambda, a/h) \quad (22)$$

Eq. (22) involves a double integral, which can be performed numerically for any given distribution of the tangential force per unit area q_1 .

Eq. (22) can be rewritten in the following dimensionless form:

$$\delta\left(\frac{\hat{r}}{h}, \frac{a}{h}\right) = \frac{2\pi h^2 T_3}{3F_3} = \frac{3\mu}{2\pi} \left(\frac{h}{a}\right)^2 \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \int_0^{a/h} \frac{\left[1 - \tilde{\lambda}^2 \left(\frac{h}{a}\right)^2\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (\lambda - \tilde{\lambda} \cos \theta) \tilde{\lambda} d\tilde{\lambda}}{[\lambda^2 + \tilde{\lambda}^2 - 2\lambda\tilde{\lambda} \cos \theta + 1]^{\frac{5}{2}}} \quad (23)$$

The function δ is plotted as a function of $\frac{\hat{r}}{h}$ for various values of $\frac{a}{h}$ in Fig. 7. Note that, for any value of $\frac{\hat{r}}{h}$, δ vanishes at $\frac{\hat{r}}{h} = 0$, i.e. if the transducer center is aligned with the point force. Also, the function δ

Fig. 7. Influence of the contact size on the stress at a point-like transducer at distance \hat{r} from the contact center, as produced by a tangent force with Hertzian distribution on a circular area of radius a . Black curve is a point force; red $a/h = 0.2$, green $a/h = 0.5$, blue $a/h = 0.7$, magenta $a/h = 1$, pink $a/h = 1.5$, violet $a/h = 2$.

Fig. 8. FEM model and mesh details on Ansys.

peaks at a value of $\frac{\hat{r}}{h}$ increasing from 0.5 for a point force to higher values as $\frac{a}{h}$ increases.

Consider that these results apply to the case of a point transducer and have only qualitative significance due to the half-space approximation employed. We will not pursue any further analysis for a distributed transducer, which will be extensively treated numerically. However, this analytical formulation oriented our numerical simulations, suggesting that the presence of a tangential component may show up through a peak of the normal stress at some distance from the peak of the normal contribution. The latter distance increases as the dimensionless radius of the contact area (a/h) increases, i.e. provided either L or R/h increase.

2.4. Finite elements model

The numerical approach employed in our simulations is now discussed, which focuses on the behavior of real configurations where the protective layer has finite thickness.

The protective elastomer layer was assumed to fill a region of space consisting of a cylinder of radius d_1 and height h , with a vertical rectangular cross section and d_1 much larger than the radii of both the sensor and the indenter (Fig. 8). The layer was modeled as an elastic material (PDMS with $E = 30$ MPa or Dragon skin with $E = 152$ kPa). To prevent any translations and rotations, a fixed support representing the rigid substrate of the transducer was set at the bottom surface of the

elastomer layer, where the transducer was located. The indenter was assumed to be hemispherical and aligned with the transducer center. It was treated as a linear elastic material, with the mechanical properties of steel, namely $E = 200$ GPa, $\nu = 0.30$ and $\rho = 7.850$ kg m⁻³. In the case of a purely normal load, the contact between the indenter and the soft layer was assumed to be *frictionless*. The load F_3 was applied by the indenter on the top surface of the e-skin, thus replicating the experimental indentation procedure. In the more general case of an arbitrarily oriented force, including both normal and tangential components, the contact was described as frictional.

The software chosen for the present simulations is ANSYS Workbench 2019 R3. The geometry and loads of the indentation process in the purely normal force case, depicted in Fig. 8, allow one to adopt a 2D axis-symmetric model instead of 3D ones. As a consequence, the computational cost is lower. PLANE183 was the element used to mesh the model. The 2D element has quadrilateral shape, is composed by 4 nodes and ensures good performances simulating great deformations of the soft protective layer. The size of the 2D element was set to 4×10^{-5} m. CONTA172 and SURF153 are the elements chosen for the contact. A mesh convergence check was performed to optimize the accuracy of the solution. When the protective layer thickness is 2 mm, the number of elements is 77 347, and the number of nodes is 226 029. The processor used to perform the simulations was Intel®Core™ i9-9900K, CPU @ 3.60 GHz, with a 32.0 GB RAM. The computational time for a single simulation was 140 min. The meshed model is shown in Fig. 8: green elements for the rigid indenter, light blue elements for the elastic protective layer and red color for fixed constraints and displacements. It is crucial to acknowledge that, in the presence of a tangential force component, the model can no longer be described through a 2D axisymmetric geometry and a 3D representation becomes necessary. This change is needed due to the significance of force orientation and the need to expand the analysis to include an array of transducers capable of capturing the direction of the tangential force component. The model is meshed through hexahedral elements, ensuring good results simulating the soft protective layer.

The value of r_t (transducer radius) was chosen based on the current technology of the PVDF sensor [14] (=1 mm), whilst the value of h was optimized, such to maximize the average normal stress experienced by the transducer. Results suggested assuming a value of h of 2 mm as a compromise, noting that silicone delamination would likely occur for lower values of the thickness. The indenter radius R was varied between 1 mm and 10 mm in order to test the response for different values of the ratio R/h .

The numerical model also allowed to test to what extent the solution depended on the elastic nature of the material employed to simulate the mechanical response of the e-skin. As the mechanical properties of a dragon skin are nearer to those of a hyperelastic material, few tests were also performed adopting the latter assumption.

The average normal stress \bar{T}_3 was evaluated on a path, emulating a section of the transducer.

An optimization of the simulations based on automatic variations of the geometric parameters of the model was adopted in order to speed up the procedure.

Table 1 reports the values of e-skin parameters.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Half-space model versus finite thickness solution

We have preliminarily repeated the early numerical simulations for the finite thickness case reported in [13], referring to a distributed normal force and a distributed transducer.

The earlier results were obtained with the help of a different software (COMSOL) that is no longer available to us and are shown as green diamonds in Fig. 9, where the early dependence of σ on a/h is adopted. In the same figure, the analytical solution is also reported as a blue solid

Table 1
E-skin parameters.

Parameter values
$r_i = 1$ mm
$h = 2$ mm
$F_3 = 1\text{--}10$ N
$E = 152$ kPa
$\nu = 0.49$
$R = 2\text{--}10$ mm
$d_{33} = -30$ pC/N

Fig. 9. Simulation results obtained in [13] for the finite thickness case (green markers) are compared with the present results (red markers) obtained performing a mesh optimization procedure. A comparison between the Boussinesq analytical model for the half-space (blue line) is also made with a numerical mesh-optimized solution for the numerically simulated half-space configuration ($H/h = 10$, see Fig. 10) of 2. The value of r_i/h was invariably fixed at 0.5.

line. The discrepancy between the green diamonds (finite thickness, numerical) and the blue line (half-space, analytical) was attributed to the inadequacy of the half-space model when applied to protective layers of finite thickness. However, at a more careful examination, it turns out that this is only part of the explanation. Indeed, repeating the calculations with the help of the new software, it was ascertained that part of the problem was numerical, in that the original mesh was insufficiently refined. Then, a mesh optimization was performed, which led to results (red diamonds in Fig. 9) closer to the analytical solution.

With the help of the optimized mesh, a simple check of the effectiveness and accuracy of our numerical model was carried out.

The half-space configuration is reproduced, where h denotes the depth below the top surface of the protective layer at which the transducer was embedded and must not be confused with the thickness H of the protective layer itself (Fig. 10).

In order to simulate the half-space configuration, we then adopted a value for H sufficiently larger than h ($H/h = 10$) and checked that the numerical solution for this case tended to the analytical solution presented in [13] for fixed values of r_i/h and R/h . The numerical results for this case are plotted as black diamonds in Fig. 9 and exhibit a perfect agreement with the analytical solution presented in [13].

3.2. Results of numerical simulations for the finite thickness case: normal force

Next, a sequence of numerical simulations is performed for the finite thickness case, using the elastic model for the protective layer. The thickness of the layer was fixed at 2 mm whilst the radius of the indenter was varied to generate six curves, each representing a different

Fig. 10. Sketch of the numerically simulated half-space configuration.

value of R/h . We limited the chosen values of R/h to a physically and technologically reasonable range (R between 0.5 and 10 mm, h from 1 to 5 mm). The value of r_i/h was again fixed at 0.5 and the value of the dimensionless parameter L was varied, for given E and R , changing the value of the indentation force F_3 . Fig. 11 shows an example of the Ansys output for the indentation force of 1 N. Results are plotted for the total deformation of the soft protective layer [m], the normal stress T_3 [Pa], the contact pressure between the indenter and the soft protective layer [Pa] and the equivalent strain of the soft layer [m/m]. The \bar{T}_3 values were then processed into the model.

Results are plotted as dotted lines in Fig. 12. In the same figure, we have also plotted as solid lines the corresponding curves for the Boussinesq half-space model shown in Fig. 3. Comparison is instructive. Indeed, the monotonically decreasing trend of all the curves is confirmed. However, significant quantitative differences exist between the finite thickness numerical and the half-space analytical solutions. This is not surprising. Indeed, the reader should recall that, in the finite case, h is the thickness of the protective layer and the transducer is embedded at the interface between the elastic protective layer and the rigid substrate. On the contrary, in the half-space case, the transducer is embedded, at depth h , in the elastic protective layer, hence the physical configuration and the boundary conditions of the mathematical problem differ in the two cases.

The trends predicted by Fig. 12 appear to be physically sensible. This can be demonstrated using qualitative arguments.

Indeed:

- As R/h decreases (say it tends to vanish) keeping F_3 and E fixed, then σ tends to a constant value (independent of L). If the limit $R/h \rightarrow 0$ is achieved keeping R fixed and letting $h \rightarrow \infty$, then, recalling Eq. (6), one finds that \bar{T}_3 tends to vanish. This is quite reasonable, as, increasing the layer thickness h , the effect of the contact force spreads over an increasing area of the bottom interface where the transducer is located. On the contrary, if the

Fig. 11. Example of FEM results on Ansys: the total deformation of the protective layer [m] (a), the normal stress (namely T_3) [Pa] (b), the contact pressure [Pa] (c) and the equivalent strain [m/m] (d) are plotted.

Fig. 12. The plot shows, for the case of a purely normal force aligned with the transducer, results for σ as a function of L , obtained by the present numerical simulations for different values of R/h (dotted lines): orange is $R/h = 0.5$, magenta is $R/h = 1$, red is $R/h = 2$, blue is $R/h = 3$, green is $R/h = 4$ and black is $R/h = 5$. The ratio r_t/h was kept fixed ($r_t/h = 0.5$). Also shown (solid lines) are the corresponding curves for the Boussinesq half-space model shown in Fig. 3.

limit $R/h \rightarrow 0$ is achieved keeping h fixed and letting $R \rightarrow 0$, then Eq. (6) predicts an increasing value for $\overline{T_3}$, which is also reasonable on physical ground. Indeed, a reduction of R with h fixed implies that the effect of the contact force concentrates within a decreasing portion of the bottom interface.

- As R/h increases by increasing R , while keeping F_3 and E fixed, then L decreases and σ also decreases. This is again quite reasonable as increasing R (with h fixed), implies that the effect of the contact force spreads over an increasing area of the bottom interface.

Similar arguments can be offered to interpret the effect of variations of the contact force F_3 or of the elastic modulus E for given values of R/h . This exercise is left to the reader.

The above results for the finite thickness case can then be used to calculate the dimensionless charge output of the e-skin, as a function of L for different values of R/h . Indeed, using Eq. (9) and results of the numerical simulations for σ plotted in Fig. 12, one finds the dependence of \hat{Q} on L plotted in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13. The plot shows, for the case of a purely normal force aligned with the transducer, the dependence of the dimensionless charge \hat{Q} on the dimensionless parameter L obtained for different values of R/h (see legend) by the present numerical simulations for the case of an elastic protective layer of finite thickness with $r_t/h = 0.5$.

Fig. 14. The plot shows, for the case of a purely normal force aligned with the transducer, the dependence of the dimensionless charge \hat{Q} on the dimensionless parameter L obtained for different values of R/h (see legend) by the present numerical simulations for the case of an elastic protective layer of finite thickness with $r_t/h = 0.2$.

Before we discuss how the above results can be employed, let us point out that the dependence of the solution on the chosen value of the parameter r_t/h does not appear to be qualitatively significant although quantitative differences are indeed found. This is demonstrated by a comparison between Figs. 13 and 14. The latter plot shows results of the simulations for a value of r_t/h (0.2) smaller than that adopted previously (0.5). Although the monotonically decreasing trend of \hat{Q} as L increases is confirmed, however the output signal for $r_t/h = 0.2$ diverges increasingly from the output signal for $r_t/h = 0.5$ as R/h decreases.

Our FEM simulations have so far relied on the assumption that the center of the transducer is vertically aligned with the indenter axis.

The next step is to relax the above constraint allowing the contact force to be centered at some horizontal distance \hat{r} from the transducer center (Fig. 15). Therefore, a finite element analysis was carried out using ANSYS, with fixed values of R/h (3) and r_t/h (0.5), and two different values of the normal contact force (1 N, 2 N), such that L attained the values 0.18 and 0.37, respectively. Results are shown in

Fig. 15. \hat{r} is the distance between the axis of symmetry of the transducer and that of the indenter.

Fig. 16. The charge response of the transducer is plotted as a function of the dimensionless transducer-indenter distance \hat{r}/h and for different values of L , in the case of a purely normal force ($R/h = 3$, $r_t/h = 0.5$).

Fig. 16, where \hat{Q} is plotted versus \hat{r}/h . The plot suggests that the charge response of the transducer (say, the modulus of \hat{Q}) decays rapidly as \hat{r}/h increases. When the projection of the indenter falls outside the transducer, then the modulus of the charge response decays more rapidly. Also note that for the chosen value of $R/h (=3)$, results in Fig. 16 suggest that the effect of the normal force is felt only within a restricted region around the transducer.

3.3. Results for an arbitrarily oriented force

Finally, the constraint of a normally oriented contact force is relaxed, allowing for frictional contact between the indenter and the soft protective layer. Below, the tangential component of the contact force will be aligned with the \mathbf{e}_1 direction (see Fig. 6). The friction coefficient used was 0.4, as experimentally measured in [20].

Fig. 17 plots the dimensionless charge response of the transducer as a function of L and for $\hat{r}/h = 0$, for given values of $R/h = 3$ and $r_t/h = 0.5$. Under the specified conditions, the curve of Fig. 17 provides the required extension of the previous model for the sole normal force (see Fig. 13). Similar plots can be constructed for different values of R/h and r_t/h , as did for the case of a purely normal force. We do not pursue this goal herein, as it would not add any further contribution to the qualitative understanding of the process. As it will be discussed in the next section, in the practical application where an array of transducers will be used, plots of this type might allow to reconstruct the force from the transducer whose charge response is the highest. The same transducer allows one to roughly locate the position of the indenter, within the spatial resolution of the sensor array. However, a more precise and independent measure of \hat{r} is needed for force reconstruction.

Fig. 17. The dimensionless charge response of the transducer is plotted as a function of L , for the case of a force oriented arbitrarily, thus possessing both tangential and normal components ($R/h = 3$, $r_t/h = 0.5$).

Note that the presence of the tangential component of the contact force breaks the axial symmetry of the charge response. Hence, the variation of \hat{Q} cannot be simply associated with the dimensionless distance \hat{r}/h , but must be complemented with some information on the direction in which the transducer is displaced. Fig. 18 plots the dimensionless charge response of the transducer as a function of the dimensionless transducer-indenter distance \hat{r}/h , in the direction of the tangential component of the contact force. The value of L was chosen as 0.045, i.e. the smallest value employed in the case of a purely normal force (see Fig. 16), as the ANSYS software did not allow higher values of L when the tangential component was added. Fig. 18 is instructive as it shows that the contribution of the tangential component of the contact force is as important as that of the normal force. It was expected that the contribution of the tangential component would appear as an oscillation at a dimensionless distance \hat{r}/h around 0.7. This was suggested by Fig. 7. Indeed, the value of a/h corresponding to $L = 0.045$ and $R/h = 3$ is 0.9, and for such value of a/h Fig. 7 shows a peak in the response for a value of \hat{r}/h around 0.7. The reason such oscillation does not show up might depend on different factors, e.g. the low chosen value for L or the fact that curves in Fig. 7 were computed considering a point transducer rather than an extended one, as done in the numerical simulations. This notwithstanding, a different method to find a signature of the tangential force component is suggested below.

Indeed, using the symmetry break due to the tangential force component, its direction can be extracted from a 2D map of the normal stress response on the transducer plane. Fig. 19 shows the distribution of the dimensionless normal stress as defined in Eq. (23), along two rays centered at the vertical projection of the indenter axis on the transducer plane. The red curve corresponds to a ray aligned with the \mathbf{e}_1 direction (i.e. the direction of the tangential force), whereas the black curve is associated with a direction orthogonal to \mathbf{e}_1 . It is not surprising that the response in the direction of the tangential force is maximal.

4. The numerical model as basic tool for sensor design, sensor calibration and force reconstruction

The plots presented in the previous section should be taken as our new proposed design tool for the manufacturing of new sensors.

Indeed, the main goal of sensor design is the choice of the thickness of the soft layer such to maximize the sensor sensitivity, i.e. the expected range of values of the charge output in response to an expected range of values of L . The latter is known once the range of indentation forces and indenter radii required in any specific application are given. Moreover, technology constrains the value of r_t within a fairly restricted range. For any given thickness h , ranges of R/h and r_t/h

Fig. 18. The dimensionless charge response of the transducer is plotted as a function of the dimensionless transducer-indenter distance \hat{r}/h for a fixed value of L (0.045), for the case of a purely normal force (blue curve), and normal and tangential forces (red curve). The dotted line corresponds to the purely tangential contribution, obtained as a difference between the red and blue curves ($R/h = 3$, $r_t/h = 0.5$).

Fig. 19. The dimensionless normal stress $\delta = \frac{2\pi h^2 T_3}{3F_3}$ is plotted for two rays centered at the vertical projection of the indenter axis on the transducer plane. The red curve identifies the direction of the tangential force component, while the black line corresponds to a ray orthogonal to the previous one ($L = 0.045$, $R/h = 3$, $r_t/h = 0.5$).

are then defined. Next, Fig. 17 allows one to evaluate the expected range of values of the dimensionless charge output and consequently its dimensional range associated with the d_{33} piezoelectric coefficient. The latter is the important information needed to size the electronic interface of the e-skin. As the slope of the \hat{Q} vs. L line (that controls the sensor sensitivity) increases for increasing values of r_t/h , the final choice of h ultimately arises from technological constraints and the adequate number of sensors in the sensing area (spatial resolution of the sensing system). In this respect, it is crucial to point out that the spatial distribution of the transducers is a further important design parameter of an electronic skin. Indeed, in principle, the possibility exists that parts of the artificial skin be blind to the contact force. It is precisely the scope of the e-skin design, subject to given constraints (eg. minimum/maximum contact forces and taxel radius), to choose the appropriate spatial distribution of the transducers to avoid any blind conditions.

These ideas are illustrated in Fig. 20.

However, a note of caution is in order. The above approach assumes linearity between the generated charge and the average normal stress \bar{T}_3 . This needs an accurate integration of the sensor array into the rigid substrate, which should also be perfectly flat. Controlling the fabrication process to a high degree might be difficult in practice. This suggests a third useful way to employ our model, namely as a practical tool for sensor calibration. Indeed, from the dimensionless formulation presented above, one readily derives dimensional calibration curves \hat{Q} vs. F_3 , associated with given values of the physical parameters. Note that, in the context of the present framework, the tangential component of the contact force is immediately obtained knowing the friction coefficient μ . An example of dimensional calibration curves is given in Fig. 21. Next, comparing the predicted charge with the real one allows one to construct a calibration matrix to be used for tactile data processing to compensate for actual differences in sensor behavior due to the fabrication process.

In addition, the monotonic dependence of the dimensionless charge \hat{Q} on L displayed by Fig. 17 makes it feasible to tackle the inverse model, namely that of reconstructing the contact force from the knowledge of the charge measured as the sensor output. However, this is fairly straightforward only provided the contact force is normal and aligned with the transducer. Indeed, under these conditions, once \hat{Q} is known, one readily calculates \hat{Q} from Eq. (9). Using Fig. 13 (or a similar plot for the specific value of r_t/h) the value of L associated with the calculated value \hat{Q} is then immediately found and, recalling the definition of L (Eq. (5)), the normal indentation force F_3 is calculated. Two features make the inverse problem much more challenging in the general case: firstly, the contact force is not necessarily aligned with a transducer, secondly the direction of the tangential component is a-priori not known. The above two issues can possibly be tackled as follows. By considering the outputs of the array of transducers, the transducer providing the highest response can be identified and the direction of the tangential component can be possibly retrieved from the asymmetry of the heat map on the transducer plane. Moreover, a method would be needed to estimate the distance between the center of the contact area and the axis of the transducer with the highest response, namely \hat{r} . In these conditions, the F_3 (normal) component of the indentation force can be extracted as for the purely normal force described previously in this paragraph, though using Fig. 17 for the \hat{Q} vs. L plot. The corresponding F_t tangential component can be calculated as μF_3 . This process is illustrated in Fig. 20. Alternatively, one may refer to the model employed to address the general inverse problem in a previous paper [12] for a configuration involving an array of transducers and a continuous distribution of the contact force. However, that approach assumed that the direct problem could be solved using the half-space Boussinesq solution, an assumption whose limits have been ascertained in the present work. Extending the latter algorithm to the finite layer case is an effort which appears to be both complex and computationally heavy. However, the importance of this issue will deserve further work in the near future. Furthermore, validating the above procedure will deserve an extended experimental campaign. The latter would also allow us to test the role of viscoelasticity, which is known to characterize some elastomeric materials employed as protective layers.

5. Concluding remarks

Our model-based approach was developed from the previous investigation presented in [13] for the normal case and extended to account for the tangential force component. The framework has been formulated in a dimensionless fashion, which has an advantage in terms of generality and its possible effective use in real applications. The present model is not restricted to a specific material employed for the skin cover layer and can be easily extended to other types of transducers, provided that the latter read pressure and convert it into an electrical signal. Indeed, the relationship between the applied force

Fig. 20. Synthetic block diagram of the uses of our model, used as an e-skin design tool and calibration tool (predictive model) and for the force reconstruction (inverse model).

Fig. 21. The dimensional calibration curves Q vs. F_3 for different values of R/h , at fixed $r_t/h = 0.5$.

and the average normal stress received by the transducer is completely independent of the transducer type as it derives from the solution for the elastic problem within the soft protective layer, which has been obtained both analytically and through numerical simulations. The transduction mechanism itself is only included in Eq. (1). For any transducer, which responds proportionally to the average normal stress it receives as input, the whole framework would not change.

As discussed in Section 3.2, the main achievement of our work is the development of a general tool for design and calibration of soft artificial skins (predictive model). We have constructed a direct model able to

compute the response of a transducer (or an array of transducers) to a contact force, modeled as Hertzian. For a fixed geometry of the sensor array and for known parameters of the contact problem (indenter radius, force and position of the indenter on the surface), the transducer output can be directly predicted. In this perspective, the present model can be used as a design tool, notably to optimize the materials and geometry of the sensor array (taxel radius, pitch, spatial arrangement; thickness of the soft layer; ...) for given application requirements. As discussed in the previous section, solving the inverse problem, namely reconstructing the magnitude and direction of the contact force and its position from the transducer output, is much more challenging. A possible approach is illustrated in Fig. 20.

The current framework suggests a number of future extensions. The strength of our approach lies in its incremental development facilitated by a model-based strategy. We start by focusing on rigid indenters, but these constraints can be relaxed in the next steps. This generalized approach can be expanded to nonlinear skin behavior, and viscoelasticity. The possibly soft nature of the indenter can also be accounted for in the model: in this case, an appropriate “soft” contact model must be available if an analytical approach is pursued or the soft nature of the indenter material must be directly integrated into the numerical approach. Currently, the approach is static and can effectively address cases where contact forces vary slowly over time, yet it has the potential for dynamic study extension, which would enable to reconstruct the variation of contact forces or contact area in time. Given that human perception of softness is closely linked to the spread rate of the contact area, extracting this information from tactile data could drive haptic feedback systems for softness perception. However, embedding such algorithms into electronic systems could become a bottleneck in terms of latency for real-time system usage.

Nomenclature

a	Contact area radius
\bar{T}_3	Average normal stress
Q	Transducer charge
\hat{Q}	Dimensionless transducer charge
σ	Dimensionless normal stress at the transducer (frictionless case)
δ	Dimensionless normal stress at the point transducer (frictional case)
L	F_3/R^2E
$\hat{\rho}$	Misalignment between transducer and indenter
μ	Friction coefficient
r_t	Taxel radius
h	Soft layer thickness
E	Dragon skin Young's Modulus
ν	Dragon Skin Poisson ratio
F_3	Normal force
$F_1; F_t$	Tangential force
R	Indenter radius
d_{33}	PVDF Piezoelectric coefficient

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Chiara Micheli: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Giovanni Berselli:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Lucia Seminara:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Giovanni Berselli reports financial support was provided by European Union. Lucia Seminara reports financial support was provided by European Union. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

Acknowledgments

This work was partially supported by AI-Powered Manipulation System for Advanced Robotic Service, Manufacturing and Prosthetics (IntelliMan) project, Italy EU H2022 under Grant 101070136. We wish to thank three anonymous referees for their constructive criticism that has definitely allowed considerable improvement of the present manuscript.

References

- [1] Piazza C, Grioli G, Catalano M, Bicchi A. A century of robotic hands. *Annu Rev Control Robot Auton Syst* 2019;2:1–32.
- [2] Cutkosky M, Jourdain J, Wright P. Skin materials for robotic fingers. In: *Proceedings. 1987 IEEE international conference on robotics and automation. Vol. 4, IEEE; 1987, p. 1649–54.*
- [3] Kandel ER, Schwartz JH, Jessell TM, Siegelbaum S, Hudspeth AJ, Mack S, et al. *Principles of neural science, vol. 4, McGraw-hill New York; 2000.*
- [4] Vallbo AB, Johansson RS, et al. Properties of cutaneous mechanoreceptors in the human hand related to touch sensation. *Hum Neurobiol* 1984;3(1):3–14.

- [5] Massari L, Fransvea G, D'Abbraccio J, Filosa M, Terruso G, Aliperta A, D'Alesio G, Zaltieri M, Schena E, Palermo E, et al. Functional mimicry of ruffini receptors with fibre Bragg gratings and deep neural networks enables a bio-inspired large-area tactile-sensitive skin. *Nat Mach Intell* 2022;4(5):425–35.
- [6] Boutry CM, Negre M, Jorda M, Vardoulis O, Chortos A, Khatib O, Bao Z. A hierarchically patterned, bioinspired e-skin able to detect the direction of applied pressure for robotics. *Science Robotics* 2018;3(24):eaau6914.
- [7] Yuan W, Dong S, Adelson EH. Gelsight: High-resolution robot tactile sensors for estimating geometry and force. *Sensors* 2017;17(12):2762.
- [8] Bicchi A, De Rossi D, Scilingo EP. The role of the contact area spread rate in haptic discrimination of softness. *IEEE Trans Robot Autom* 2000;16(5):496–504.
- [9] Pagnanelli G, Ciotti S, Lepora N, Bicchi A, Bianchi M. Model-based compliance discrimination via soft tactile optical sensing and optical flow computation: A biomimetic approach. *IEEE Robot Autom Lett* 2023.
- [10] Ward-Cherrier B, Pestell N, Cramphorn L, Winstone B, Giannaccini ME, Rossiter J, Lepora NF. The tactip family: Soft optical tactile sensors with 3d-printed biomimetic morphologies. *Soft Robot* 2018;5(2):216–27.
- [11] Sun H, Kuchenbecker KJ, Martius G. A soft thumb-sized vision-based sensor with accurate all-round force perception. *Nat Mach Intell* 2022;4(2):135–45.
- [12] Seminara L, Capurro M, Valle M. Tactile data processing method for the reconstruction of contact force distributions. *Mechatronics* 2015;27:28–37.
- [13] Seminara L. Modeling electronic skin response to normal distributed force. *Sensors* 2018;18(2):459.
- [14] Fares H, Abbass Y, Valle M, Seminara L. Validation of screen-printed electronic skin based on piezoelectric polymer sensors. *Sensors* 2020;20(4):1160.
- [15] Nalwa HS. *Ferroelectric polymers: chemistry, physics, and applications.* CRC Press; 1995.
- [16] IEEE Standard on Piezoelectricity. ANSI/IEEE Std 176-1987, 1988, p. i–66. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/IEEESTD.1988.79638>.
- [17] Saleh M, Abbass Y, Ibrahim A, Valle M. Experimental assessment of the interface electronic system for PVDF-based piezoelectric tactile sensors. *Sensors* 2019;19(20):4437.
- [18] Johnson KL, Johnson KL. *Contact mechanics.* Cambridge University Press; 1987.
- [19] Boussinesq J. *Application des potentiels à l'étude de l'équilibre et du mouvement des solides élastiques.* 1885.
- [20] Berthold R, Burgner-Kahrs J, Wangenheim Mea. Investigating frictional contact behavior for soft material robot simulations. *Meccanica* 2023;58:2165–76. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11012-023-01719-5>.

Chiara Micheli Chiara Micheli was born in La Spezia, Italy in 1997. She received the M.S. degree in Mechanical Engineering — curriculum Mechatronics, from the University of Genoa, Genoa, Italy, in 2021. She is currently a Ph.D student at University of Genoa in Science and Technologies for electronics and telecommunication engineering. She is working on robotic systems based on tactile sensing for biomedical application.

Giovanni Berselli Giovanni Berselli is Full Professor and Chair of Design Methods for Industrial Engineering at the University of Genova, and Affiliated Researcher with Italian Institute of Technology. He is a Fellow of the ASME and Chair of ASME Italy Section. He has been Affiliated Scientist at: Harvard Medical School, Massachusetts General Hospital, German Aerospace Agency (DLR), University of Twente, Monash University, School of Advanced Studies — University of Navarra. He has authored more than 200 publications in international journals or proceedings and edited two books. His scientific activity is focused on: (i) robot hands design; (ii) compliant/soft actuators; (iii) energy-aware industrial robotics.

Lucia seminara Lucia Seminara graduated from the University of Genoa (IT) in 1999 with a degree in Physics and pursued her doctorate at EPFL (CH). Following a short tenure in the industry, she currently holds the position of Associate Professor within the Department of Electronic Engineering of the University of Genoa. Her research focuses on developing electronic systems to artificially restore the sense of touch. Her main current interests relate to closing the sensorimotor control loop in different applications (eg prosthetics). She co-authored a patented method reconstructing contact force distribution from eskin sensor data. She is IEEE member.